

Arthroscopic Anterior Cruciate Ligament Reconstruction: A Comparative Clinical Outcome between Transtibial and Anteromedial Portal Techniques in Femoral Tunnelling

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Abstract:

Introduction: ACL reconstruction has evolved as gold standard for ACL injuries. However, anatomic reconstruction of ACL is of utmost importance to have best outcomes. Newly reconstructed ACL should control the anterior translation as well as internal rotation, for which appropriate anatomical femoral tunnel placement is of absolute necessity. There are two methods of securing femoral tunnel. Anteromedial portal technique and transtibial technique. The study aims to compare the outcomes using both these methods.

Materials and Methods: Patients with clinically diagnosed and radiologically diagnosed ACL tears are recruited in the study and divided into two groups, viz, transtibial group (TT group) and Anteromedial portal group (AMP group). After surgery, the outcomes are compared clinically and subjective scores are compared.

Results: The mean age of the participants is 31.5 years. There is male preponderance in both the groups and right side is more commonly affected. IKDC scores are better in the AMP group compared to TT group. However, Lysholm scores are better in the later. Clinical outcome with respect to pivot shift test is better in AMP group compared to TT group.

Conclusion: AMP technique provides more anatomical femoral tunnel placement compared to TT technique with respect to clinical outcomes. But care should be taken about posterior femoral cortex blow out.

Keywords: ACL, Transtibial Portal, Anteromedial Portal, Femoral Tunnel.

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Introduction

Anterior Cruciate ligament reconstruction techniques have evolved over past few years. Anatomic ACL reconstruction is of utmost importance, as ACL reconstruction not only controls the anterior tibial translation but also internal rotation. Proper placement of femoral tunnel is essential to restore the knee kinematics to the best possible extent [1].

As the advances in arthroscopic ACL reconstruction evolved, there are three methods of achieving femoral attachment with single bundle Hamstring graft. They are outside-in technique for femoral attachment through lateral approach, single incision transtibial and anteromedial portals [1]. Exact anatomic reconstruction of the ACL is essential to minimise complications like residual instability,

loss of motion, surgical failure and post-traumatic osteoarthritis [2]. The femoral attachment lies lower in the notch approximately around 11'o clock position to 8'o clock position in the lateral femoral condyle. The obliquity of the graft also plays an important role in the kinematics of the knee after reconstruction.

The transtibial technique (TT) may lead to difficulty with instrumentation, more vertical placement of graft and other problems which may lead to non-anatomic placement of the graft [3]. The anteromedial portal (AMP) is being explored recently, as it is likely to offer better exposure and more anatomical placement of the graft in femoral tunnel [4]. Hence it is prudent to understand the

advantages and disadvantages of each technique to ensure optimal surgical outcome.

Though there are many cadaveric studies which compare the two techniques, there is paucity of the studies comparing clinical outcome following both the techniques.

The present study aims to explore the merits and de-merits of the Transtibial (TT) and Anteromedial portal (AMP) techniques in achieving an anatomical femoral attachment of single bundle Hamstring graft in ACL reconstruction.

Aim: To compare the functional outcome between the anteromedial portal and transtibial techniques of arthroscopic ACL reconstruction.

Materials and Methods

Study Design: Retrospective and Prospective cohort study

Study Period: 11 months

Sample Size: 40

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Age between 18-50 years
2. No associated fractures
3. No previous knee pathology
4. A complete ACL tear confirmed clinically and through MRI
5. Single bundle hamstring autografts

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Injury less than three weeks
2. Pre-existing primary or secondary arthritis
3. Revision surgery
4. Multi ligament injuries
5. ACL avulsion
6. Fractures around the knee
7. Different fixation methods

Methodology

The cases which met the above-mentioned inclusion and exclusion criteria and those who have given consent are recruited in the study. After thorough clinical examination and appropriate pre-anaesthetic check-up, the cases are divided into two groups randomly. After initial diagnostic arthroscopy through standard anterolateral portal, ACL reconstruction is done using single bundle Hamstring graft

Method for transtibial tunnel technique (TT technique):

- A femoral guide with an appropriate offset (e.g., with an 8-mm graft, a femoral guide with a 5-mm offset is used) is introduced into the joint through the tibial tunnel.
- It is placed in the posterior aspect of the notch.
- Knee is flexed to approximately 70 to 90 degrees
- A beath needle is introduced in a position which has been determined by the femoral guide (usually at around the 11 o'clock position for the right knee or approximately the 1 o'clock position for the left knee).
- The beath needle is then over-drilled with a reamer corresponding to the size of the graft diameter and a depth of 30mm.
- Graft fixation is performed with interference screws in both tibial and the femoral tunnel.

Method for Anteromedial portal technique (AMP technique):

- The knee placed in maximum flexion between 125 to 130 degrees.
- A femoral guide with an appropriate offset is introduced into the joint through the anteromedial portal.
- With the aim of the femoral guide, a beath needle is then placed into the centre of the ACL anatomic insertion (usually at approximately the 10 o'clock position for the right knee or at roughly the 2 o'clock position for the left knee) about 8mm lateral to the PCL.
- With the knee in full flexion, the beath needle is over-drilled with a reamer corresponding to the size of the graft diameter and a depth of 30 mm (it is ensured that 2-3mm of bone remains as the posterior wall of the femoral tunnel)
- Graft is fixed with the help of an interference screw.

Tibial fixation is done using the interference screw through the tibial tunnel. Saline wash is given to clear off the debris and wound is closed. A standard, uniform ACL rehabilitation protocol is used to all the patients of both the groups.

Patients are assessed pre-operatively and 6 months post-operatively with IKDC scores, Lysholm score and clinical examination.

Post-operative radiographs are also taken to assess the position of the interference screws [Fig-1 and Fig-2 showing post-operative ACL reconstruction using TT and AMP technique respectively].

Figure1: Post-op TT technique

Figure 2: Post-op AMP technique

Statistical analysis:

1. Observations tabulated and analysed, qualitatively and quantitatively, using proper statistical methods on completion of the study.
2. Clinical and demographic data compared between the two groups.
3. Intergroup comparison analysed by K- Independent sample t-test.
4. An intragroup comparison analysed by Paired t-test.

Results:

The mean age of the participants is 31.5years. There is male preponderance (95%) in both the groups of ACL reconstruction. Right knee is most commonly affected and more predominant in both the groups with 75% in TT group and 55% in AMP group respectively. The tables given below illustrate the IKDC score and Lysholm score pre-operatively and post-operatively in each of the groups.

Table 1: IKDC scores pre-operatively and post-operatively:

IKDC subjective score	Pre-op	Post-op	%change
Group TT (P-value= 0.00001)			
<50%	15 (75%)	0	-75%
50-75	5 (25%)	13 (65%)	+40%
>75%	0	7 (35%)	+35%
Group AMP (P-value= 0.0052)			
<50%	8 (40%)	3 (15%)	-25%
50-75	11(55%)	7 (35%)	-20%
>75%	1(5%)	10 (50%)	+45%

Table 2: Lysholm scores pre-operatively and post-operatively

Lysholm score	Group TT	Group AMP
Pre-op	62.15±8.67	61.95±7.59
Post-op	81.70±7.69	76.75±11.68

The table given below illustrates the post-operative pivot shift test in two groups.

Table 3: PIVOT shift test post-operatively in Group TT and Group AMP

PIVOT	Group TT	Group AMP
Negative	3 (15%)	9 (45%)
Positive	17 (85%)	11 (55%)
+1	8 (40%)	9 (45%)
+2	7	2 (10%)
+3	2	0 (0%)

Discussion

An ACL injury is a common occurrence these days due to increased participation in sports and a high incidence of accidental trauma [5]. ACL deficiency causes progressive deterioration of knee function that leads to early osteoarthritis and instability in due course of time, especially in active individuals [6]. Surgical reconstruction plays an important role here, as it helps to restore normal joint kinematics and function, thereby eliminating knee instability. Early anatomical ACL reconstruction significantly reduces the risk of subsequent meniscal tears and osteoarthritis compared to delayed reconstruction [7].

Tunnel placement is important to ensure proper graft uptake [8]. It is observed that femoral tunnel is most commonly misplaced [9]. Transportal and transtibial techniques are most commonly employed to secure a femoral tunnel. However, the debate still continues about the advantages and disadvantages of each of them. The present study which includes 20 cases in each group aims to identify the former.

In the present study, the IKDC scores showed improvement from pre-operative period to post-operative period in both the groups. However, the mean subjective pre-operative IKDC score is 55.81% in TT group and the mean postoperative score is 70.29% in the anteromedial group indicating better improvement in the later. The results in the present study are similar to that of Li R et al, a systematic review and meta-analysis, where 10 studies, involving 792 patients showed better IKDC scores in AMP group [11].

On the contrary, the mean Lysholm scores were better in TT group (81.70+7.69) compared to AMP group (76.75+11.68). Healthy and near-normal knees (rating>70%) were recorded in 90%patients of the TT group and 70% patients of AMP group. However, the results in the present study differ from that of Li et al, where the Lysholm scores were better in AMP group compared to that of TT group [11]. However, these scores are subjective. Pivot shift test is an important clinical test to assess the rotational stability of the knee. Good rotational stability of knee is important to prevent re-rupture [10]. 55%patients in TT group had no or grade 1+

pivot shift test as compared to 90% of the patients in AMP group (P-value = 0.038) , indicating better post-operative rotational stability in AMP group compared to TT group. The results are similar to that of Li et al where 19 studies with 1632 participants showed increased negative pivot shift in AMP group.

However, study by Metso et al also pointed out that at 2 years follow-up there is no significant difference between both the techniques, even though the outcomes seemed better at 1 year follow up in AMP group [10]. Another study by Rahr-Wegner et al mentioned that, the revision rates were higher in the AMP group as per the Danish Knee Ligament Reconstruction Register, probably because AMP being a novel technique with steeper learning curve leading to more technical failures [12]. AMP is also sought with the risk of increased posterior wall blow out.

Limitations of the present study are small sample size and lack of randomization and lesser period of follow-up.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the present study, it can be concluded that AMP technique provides better rotational stability and early improved knee scores compared to TT technique. Nevertheless, a greater number of cases and longer duration of follow-up are essential to understand more about the complications and outcomes after following these techniques.

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